

1 **Running head:** Post-fire wood facilitates seedling regeneration

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3 POST-FIRE WOOD MANAGEMENT ALTERS WATER STRESS, GROWTH, AND
4 PERFORMANCE OF PINE REGENERATION IN A MEDITERRANEAN ECOSYSTEM

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23 ABSTRACT

24 Extensive research has focused on comparing the impacts of post-fire salvage logging
25 *versus* those of less aggressive management practices on forest regeneration. However,
26 few studies have addressed the effects of different burnt-wood management options on
27 seedling/sapling performance, or the ecophysiological mechanisms underlying differences
28 among treatments. In this study, we experimentally assess the effects of post-fire
29 management of the burnt wood on the growth and performance of naturally regenerating
30 pine seedlings (*Pinus pinaster*). Three post-fire management treatments varying in degree
31 of intervention were implemented seven months after a high-severity wildfire burned
32 Mediterranean pine forests in the Sierra Nevada, southeast Spain: a) “No Intervention”
33 (NI, all burnt trees left standing); b) “Partial Cut plus Lopping” (PCL, felling most of the
34 burnt trees, cutting off branches, and leaving all the biomass on site without mastication);
35 and c) “Salvage Logging” (SL, felling the burnt trees, piling up the logs and masticating
36 the fine woody debris). Three years after the fire, the growth, foliar nutrient
37 concentrations, and leaf carbon, nitrogen and oxygen isotopic composition ($\delta^{13}\text{C}$, $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and
38 $\delta^{15}\text{N}$) of naturally regenerating seedlings were measured in all the treatments. Pine
39 seedlings showed greatest vigor and size in the PCL treatment, whereas growth was
40 poorest in SL. The nutrient concentrations were similar among treatments, although
41 greater growth in the two treatments with residual wood present indicated higher plant
42 uptake. Seedlings in the SL treatment showed high leaf $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ values indicating
43 severe water stress, in contrast to significantly alleviated water stress indications in the
44 PCL treatment. Seedling growth and physiological performance in NI was intermediate
45 between that of PCL and SL. After six growing seasons, *P. pinaster* saplings in PCL
46 showed greater growth and cone production than SL saplings. In summary, salvage
47 logging has a detrimental effect on the ecophysiological performance and growth of
48 naturally regenerating pine seedlings, compared to alternative post-fire management
49 practices in which burnt logs and branches are left *in situ*. Improved seedling growth and
50 performance is associated with the amelioration of microsite/microclimate conditions by

51 the presence of residual burnt wood, which alleviates seedling drought stress and
52 improves nutrient availability through the decomposition of woody debris.

53

54 **Key words:** Burnt wood, facilitation, nurse structures, *Pinus pinaster*, post-fire
55 restoration, salvage harvesting.

56 **Abbreviations:** “No Intervention” (NI), “Salvage Logging” (SL), “Partial Cut plus Lopping”
57 (PCL).

58 1. INTRODUCTION

59 Fires severely burn large areas of forests every year in many parts of the world
60 (FAO, 2007). After fire, active management is a common practice in order to restore the
61 vegetation. To this end, it is customary for the local forest service (whether directly or
62 through private contractors) to remove the burnt tree trunks from the site, a process that
63 is referred to as salvage logging (SL) and that often involves the elimination of the
64 remaining woody debris such as branches and snags by chopping, mastication, fire, etc.
65 (Lindenmayer et al., 2008; McIver and Starr, 2000). Post-fire salvage logging is widely
66 implemented worldwide for multiple reasons (Brown et al., 2003; Castro et al., 2010a;
67 Lindenmayer and Noss, 2006; Lutz and Halpern, 2006; McIver and Starr, 2000). However,
68 SL commonly renders a landscape devoid of most of the woody biomass, leading to a
69 simplification of the post-fire habitat structure (Bros et al., 2011; Lindenmayer et al.,
70 2008). Despite being so widely implemented, post-fire salvage logging is currently a
71 controversial issue among restoration ecologists and forest managers (Lindenmayer et al.,
72 2008), as it can adversely affect a large set of ecosystem functions and processes such as
73 plant or animal biodiversity (Beghin et al., 2010; Castro et al., 2010b; Lindenmayer and
74 Noss, 2006; McIver and Starr, 2000), watershed runoff and erosion (Karr et al., 2004;
75 Shakesby et al., 1996), nutrient cycling (Brown et al., 1996; Marañón-Jiménez and Castro,
76 2013), plant-animal mutualistic interactions (Castro et al., 2012; Cavallero et al., 2013;
77 Rost et al., 2009), or carbon exchange with the atmosphere (Serrano-Ortiz et al., 2011; see
78 Lindenmayer et al., 2008 for a review).

79 Salvage logging in particular can have major impacts on natural post-fire tree
80 regeneration capacity. The felling and removal of burnt trees using ground-based yarding
81 techniques may increase soil erosion and compaction (Fernández et al., 2007; McIver and
82 McNeil, 2006), thus precluding seedling emergence and establishment (Castro et al., 2011;
83 Donato et al., 2006). Further, the tree seedling bank and/or resprouts already present (or
84 starting to appear) at time of salvage operations can be damaged, thus reducing seedling
85 density and regeneration capacity (Castro et al., 2011; Fernández et al., 2008; Greene et
86 al., 2006; Martínez-Sánchez et al., 1999). In contrast to these potential negative impacts of
87 salvage logging, the continued presence of residual logs, branches and other coarse woody
88 debris in unsalvaged forests can encourage tree seedling recruitment in several ways.
89 Coarse woody debris reduces solar radiation at the ground level, thereby decreasing soil
90 heating and evaporation, and consequently helping to maintain soil moisture storage
91 (Devine and Harrington, 2007; Martínez-Sánchez et al., 1999). In this way, the remaining
92 burnt wood can act as nurse structures that promote seedling establishment (Castro et al.,
93 2011). In addition, logs and other coarse woody debris represent a potentially important
94 nutrient reservoir that can slowly be incorporated into the mineral soil by decomposition
95 (Ganjegunte et al., 2004; Johnson et al., 2005; Marañón-Jiménez et al., 2013; Marañón-
96 Jiménez and Castro, 2013; Ouro et al., 2001; Zhou et al., 2007), thus becoming available
97 for the regenerating vegetation (Augusto et al., 2000; Stoddard et al., 2008). The presence
98 of burnt wood left on site after a fire might therefore improve plant regeneration both by
99 microclimatic amelioration as well as by improved nutrient supply.

100 Despite the strong negative effects that post-fire salvage logging may exert on
101 plant regeneration and its other ecological implications, there are few studies addressing
102 the underlying mechanisms that determine tree regeneration success as a function of
103 post-fire management treatment. In this study, we seek to investigate: 1) the effects that
104 residual burnt wood exerts on the growth and reproductive performance of pine
105 seedlings/saplings naturally regenerating after a fire; and 2) the ecophysiological
106 mechanisms underlying differences in plant performance resulting from different post-
107 fire management treatments. In September 2005, the Lanjarón fire burned *ca.* 3500 ha in

108 the Sierra Nevada Natural and National Park (SE Spain). Working in cooperation with the
109 local Forest Service, we established a long-term study plot in an area dominated before
110 the fire by maritime pine (*Pinus pinaster* Aiton), a serotinous pine that often regenerates
111 abundantly after fire (Fernández et al., 2008; Fernandes and Rigolot, 2007). Three
112 replicated treatments were established and they differed in both the amount and spatial
113 structure of burnt wood left on site, ranging in intensity from no intervention to
114 conventional salvage logging (see Castro et al., 2011). We monitored pine performance
115 through the sixth growing season by measuring a combination of variables related to
116 growth and reproduction. Three years after seedling establishment, we also measured leaf
117 macro- and micro-nutrient concentrations, as well as the carbon, nitrogen and oxygen
118 stable isotope ratios (^{13}C , ^{15}N and ^{18}O) of leaf dry matter.

119 The stable isotope composition of leaves can provide insight into plant water relations
120 in water-limited ecosystems (Moreno-Gutiérrez et al., 2011; Querejeta et al., 2008; Ramírez
121 et al., 2009). The carbon isotope composition of plant tissues ($\delta^{13}\text{C}$) provides a useful index
122 for assessing intrinsic water-use efficiency, *i.e.* the ratio of photosynthetic carbon fixation to
123 stomatal conductance (Dawson et al., 2002; Farquhar et al., 1989). Plant water stress can
124 reduce both the photosynthetic rate (A) and stomatal conductance (g_s), although a
125 comparatively sharper decrease of g_s normally boosts water-use efficiency ($WUE_i=A/g_s$) and
126 $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ (Dawson et al., 2002; Farquhar et al., 1989). Leaf $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ can provide a time-integrated
127 measure of plant stomatal conductance when other sources of variation (mainly differences in
128 source water $\delta^{18}\text{O}$) are small (Barbour, 2007; Barbour et al., 2002; Barbour et al., 2000;
129 Farquhar et al., 2007; Moreno-Gutiérrez et al., 2011). The relationship between plant $\delta^{18}\text{O}$
130 and g_s is inverse, so that a lower $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ value indicates higher stomatal conductance. Since
131 plant $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ is related to stomatal conductance but is not affected by photosynthetic rate, it can
132 help separate the independent effects of A and g_s on $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ (Barbour, 2007). Therefore,
133 simultaneous measurement of $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ in leaf material allows discrimination between
134 biochemical and stomatal limitations to photosynthesis (Barbour et al., 2002; Grams et al.,
135 2007; Keitel et al., 2003; Moreno-Gutiérrez et al., 2011; Querejeta et al., 2008; Scheidegger
136 et al., 2000). Plants growing in fertile, N-rich forest sites tend to show high leaf $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ since
137 they take up N that is enriched in ^{15}N . This is so because N losses from the system (by
138 leaching after nitrification, or as gaseous N through denitrification) are depleted in ^{15}N , thus
139 leaving the remaining available N for plants enriched in ^{15}N (Craine et al., 2009; Högberg,

140 1997; Högberg and Johannisson, 1993). Further, symbiotic ectomycorrhizal fungi are less
141 crucial for plant N uptake in N-rich ecosystems, and the N taken up directly by the plant is
142 comparatively more enriched in ^{15}N (Craine et al., 2009).

143

144 We hypothesized that burnt logs and branches left on site after the fire would
145 improve microclimatic conditions for naturally regenerating seedlings through shading
146 and sheltering effects (Hypothesis 1), and would also improve soil fertility in a medium to
147 longer term through nutrient release by wood decomposition (Hypothesis 2). Reduced
148 soil heating and soil moisture evaporation under the shelter of burnt trees and/or coarse
149 woody debris can result in higher soil moisture retention (Castro et al., 2011). This would
150 translate to reduced seedling water stress, which should be reflected in the carbon and
151 oxygen isotopic ratios of their leaves (Hypothesis 3). Altogether, this should lead to
152 poorer growth, vigor and overall performance of pine seedlings growing in salvaged areas
153 compared to those growing in areas with coarse woody debris left on site after the fire
154 (overall Hypothesis).

155

156 2. MATERIAL AND METHODS

157 2.1. Study site and species

158 The study site is located in Sierra Nevada Natural and National Park (SE Spain),
159 where a fire burned 1300 ha of pine forest (3420 ha in total) in September 2005. The site
160 was a *Pinus pinaster* and *P. nigra* reforestation stand at 1395-1552 m a.s.l. ($36^{\circ} 57' 9.89''\text{N}$,
161 $3^{\circ} 29' 36.24'' \text{W}$), with a tree density (measured after the fire) of 1477 ± 46 individuals per
162 ha and a basal trunk diameter of 17.7 ± 0.2 cm (mean \pm SE; Castro et al., 2011). The site is
163 located on a SW-oriented hillside (slope: $30.3 \pm 5.7\%$) with micaschist as bedrock. Climate
164 in the area is Mediterranean, with warm, dry summers and mild, rainy winters. Mean
165 annual precipitation at the site is 500 ± 50 mm (1988–2011) and mean annual temperature
166 is $11.8 \pm 0.5^{\circ}\text{C}$ at 1652 m a.s.l. (State Meteorological Agency, period 1994–2011; Ministry of
167 Environment).

168 *Pinus pinaster* Aiton grows in the western Mediterranean basin and Atlantic areas
169 of the Iberian Peninsula and southern France, from sea level to 1700 m a.s.l. (Franco,

170 1986). It is a fast-growing species that has been widely used in reforestation planting, thus
171 increasing its distribution area in the Mediterranean basin throughout the 20th century.
172 It produces serotinous cones that protect the seeds from intense heat (Reyes and Casal,
173 2002). Seeds may still be viable after short heat pulses of above 100°C (Martínez-Sánchez
174 et al., 1995), and the regeneration of the species after fire relies mostly on the aerial seed
175 bank. Abundant *P. pinaster* seedling regeneration occurred naturally in the area after the
176 fire, with seedling emergence in late February 2006 (*ca.* 6 months after the fire; Castro et
177 al., 2011).

178

179 2.2. Experimental design

180 From 21 April 2006 to 10 May 2006 (*ca.* seven months after the 2005 forest fire),
181 the local Forest Service established a 17.8 hectares plot with three randomly distributed
182 replicates of three treatments that differed in their degree of post-fire burnt wood
183 management:

- 184 1) “Non Intervention” (NI), with no post-fire management, leaving all burnt trees
185 standing.
- 186 2) “Partial Cut plus Lopping” (PCL), a treatment where about 90% of burnt trees were cut
187 and felled, with the main branches also lopped off, but leaving all the cut biomass
188 (boles and branches) *in situ* on the ground; after treatment application, felled logs
189 and branches covered 45% of the surface at 0-10 cm from the ground, 61% at 11-50
190 cm, and 9% at 51-100 cm (Castro et al., 2011).
- 191 3) “Salvage Logging” (SL), where trees were felled and limbed with the use of chainsaws.
192 Woody debris was masticated using a tractor and trunks were manually piled
193 (groups of 10-15). The Forest Service planned to remove the piled trunks with a log
194 forwarder in this SL treatment, but this step was later cancelled due to difficulties in
195 precisely operating machinery within the spatial arrangement of the plots.

196 The three treatments differed in the degree of intervention (maximum in SL,
197 intermediate in PCL, minimum in NI) and in the habitat structure generated (minimum
198 habitat complexity in SL). The PCL treatment differed from NI in the above-ground

199 habitat structure, including closer contact of burnt wood with the soil in PCL. The size of
200 the resulting nine experimental replicates averaged 2.0 ± 0.2 hectares, with no significant
201 differences in size between treatments (Kruskal-Wallis test, $P > 0.05$). All replicates were
202 homogeneous in terms of orientation (SW), slope (*ca.* 30%) and bedrock (micaschist). The
203 fire was moderate to high in intensity, consuming or totally scorching almost all tree
204 crowns. Burnt trees in the NI treatment felled during the course of the first few post-fire
205 years. The fallen fraction (measured in February of each year) was 0.0% in 2006 and 2007,
206 $13.6 \pm 2.7\%$ in 2008, $92.7 \pm 0.6\%$ in 2009 and $99.8 \pm 0.2\%$ in 2010 (Castro et al., 2012).
207 Accompanying post-fire vegetation was composed mainly of grasses and forbs, with a
208 mean aerial cover in spring 2007 of $41.5 \pm 2.4\%$ for NI, $41.6 \pm 2.7\%$ for PCL, and
209 $22.8 \pm 1.2\%$ for SL (data for non-annual species; Castro et al., 2010a).

210

211 *2.3. Seedling growth*

212 Seedling growth was monitored twice (2008 and 2012) in each experimental
213 replicate. In September 2008 (after three growing seasons) we conducted a destructive
214 sampling in order to measure seedling biomass as a growth variable. Twelve seedlings per
215 experimental replicate (108 seedlings in total) were randomly selected, cut at ground level
216 and brought to the laboratory. Herbivore damage was not detected in the area (see also
217 Castro et al., 2011), and thus no seedling had to be discarded for this reason. For each
218 seedling, we measured the following growth variables: i) total height, ii) leader-shoot
219 elongation during the growing season of 2007 (measuring the length of the leader-shoot
220 section produced in this season), iii) leader-shoot elongation during the growing season of
221 2008 (measured in a similar way), iv) basal trunk diameter, v) total biomass, vi) biomass of
222 shoots produced in 2007, vii) and biomass of shoots produced in 2008. Biomass was
223 measured after oven-drying at 60°C to constant weight (>48 h).

224 In January 2012 (after six growing seasons) we measured sapling growth in 20
225 randomly selected pines per experimental replicate (180 saplings in total). In each pine,
226 we measured total height, leader-shoot elongation during the growing season of 2011,

227 basal trunk diameter, and cone production (no cones were found in the pines at the time
228 of the previous sampling in 2008).

229

230 *2.4. Seedling nutrient concentrations*

231 Carbon and nutrient concentrations (N, P, Ca, Mg, K, Na, Fe, Mn, Zn, and Cu)
232 were measured in needles from the seedlings harvested in 2008. After drying, two
233 subsamples of needles were taken from the leader-shoot sections corresponding to the
234 elongations of 2007 and 2008 (leader-shoot elongation during the second and third year,
235 respectively). The foliar material was ground with a ball-mill and homogenized. Foliar C
236 and N concentrations were analysed by combustion at 850°C with a Leco True Spec
237 Autoanalyzer (St. Joseph, MI, USA). Ground samples were ignited to 750°C and extracts
238 were prepared by dry-ashing dissolution with HCl. From these extracts, P was
239 determined by spectrophotometry with the molybdovanadate method [Association of
240 Official Analytical Chemists (AOAC), 1975] with a Perkin Elmer 2400 spectrophotometer
241 (Waltham, MA, USA). Concentrations of the other nutrients were measured in needles of
242 the 2008 leader-shoot section only, by atomic absorption with a Perkin Elmer 5100
243 spectrometer.

244

245 *2.5. Leaf isotopic analyses*

246 Foliar $\delta^{13}\text{C}$, $\delta^{15}\text{N}$, and $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ were measured in needles from the 2008 leader-shoot
247 section (third growing season after seedling emergence) using a subsample of ground
248 material. Foliar $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ were measured in a micromass isotope ratio mass
249 spectrometer GV Instruments Iso Prime (Youngstown, OH, USA) at the Stable Isotope
250 Analysis Laboratory of University of Granada. Six standards were included for their
251 analysis after every 7-8 samples. The repeated analysis of these standards consistently
252 yielded a standard deviation <0.1‰. Foliar $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ was measured at the UC Davis Stable
253 Isotope Facility, Davis, California (USA) using a Hekatech HT Oxygen Analyzer
254 interfaced to a PDZ Europa 20-20 isotope ratio mass spectrometer (Sercon Ltd., Cheshire,
255 UK), following the method described in Kornexl et al. (1999). Leaf samples were

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256 converted by pyrolysis in a glassy carbon reactor at 1400°C to CO and H₂O, and oxygen
 257 was analysed as CO. The working standard for O isotopes analysis was microcrystalline
 258 cellulose at 30.5‰ vs.V-SMOW. The repeated analysis of these standards consistently
 259 yielded a standard deviation <0.54‰. The stable isotope composition of plant material is
 260 presented in delta notation (δ), relative to a standard:

$$261 \quad \delta = \left(\frac{R_{\text{sample}}}{R_{\text{st}}} - 1 \right) \times 1000 \text{‰}$$

262 where R is the molar ratio of the heavy to light isotopes ($R = {}^{13}\text{C}/{}^{12}\text{C}$, ${}^{15}\text{N}/{}^{14}\text{N}$ or ${}^{18}\text{O}/{}^{16}\text{O}$).
 263 R_{sample} refers to the sample and R_{st} to the international standards Vienna-Pee Dee
 264 Belemnite, atmospheric N₂ and Vienna Standard Mean Oceanic Water (V-SMOW) for C,
 265 N and O, respectively.

266

267 2.6. Data analysis

268 The effect of the treatments on pine seedlings was analysed for all variables using
 269 linear mixed models, with treatment as the fixed factor and replicate as a random factor
 270 nested within the treatment. Thus, the hierarchical model considered was:

$$271 \quad Y_{ijk} = \mu + T_i + R(T)_i + \varepsilon_{ijk}$$

272 where Y_{ijk} is the value of the dependent variable measured in the seedling ijk ; μ is the
 273 general mean; T_i is the effect of the treatment; $R(T)_i$ is the effect of replicates nested
 274 within each treatment, which accounted for the environmental variation within each
 275 treatment; and ε_{ijk} is the residual error not accounted for by the rest of factors included in
 276 the model. Contrasts were performed by the method of the restricted maximum
 277 likelihood (REML).

278 In the case of variables measured in the leader shoot elongated in both 2007 and
 279 2008 (leader-shoot length, shoot biomass, and C, N, P concentrations) the analysis was
 280 performed separately for each year since we were interested in the effect of the
 281 treatments rather than in the pattern through time. Furthermore, several processes could
 282 be interacting throughout shoot growth (*i.e.* biomass gains in the following years after the
 283 shoot elongation, nutrient allocation, etc.), confounding the effects of climatic or

284 environmental factors across years. The relationship between the nutrient concentrations
285 in needles, their isotopic composition and the growth variables were also explored by
286 Pearson product-moment correlations. Differences among treatments in the number of
287 pines that reached maturity after six years was analysed using a contingency test, whereas
288 the differences in the number of cones produced per tree were analysed with a Kruskal-
289 Wallis test (pooling data of the three replicates per treatment).

290 Data were transformed when required to achieve normality and homoscedasticity
291 (Quinn and Keough, 2009). Statistical analyses were made with JMP 7.0 software (SAS
292 Institute). Throughout the paper, mean values are followed by $\pm 1SE$.

293

294 3. RESULTS

295 3.1. Growth and leaf nutrient content

296 Three growing seasons after emergence (September 2008), pine seedlings were
297 significantly taller in the PCL and NI treatments than in SL (Table 1; Fig. 1). Total
298 seedling biomass and basal trunk diameter tended to be higher in the PCL (85.34 ± 6.41 g
299 and 11.87 ± 0.46 mm, respectively) than in NI (66.13 ± 6.23 g and 10.38 ± 0.40 mm,
300 respectively) and SL (74.76 ± 6.57 g and 11.51 ± 0.38 mm, respectively), although these
301 differences were not statistically significant (Table 1). Leader-shoot elongation and
302 biomass production were also higher in the PCL and NI treatments than in SL (Table 1;
303 Fig. 1) in 2008. The same pattern was found for the leader-shoot sections produced in the
304 previous year (2007), although differences between treatments were not statistically
305 significant at this earlier stage (Table 1; Fig. 1).

306 Six years after the fire (January 2012), pine saplings in the PCL treatment were
307 significantly taller and also showed greater seasonal shoot elongation than those in the SL
308 treatment (Table 1), whereas saplings in the NI treatment showed intermediate growth
309 (Fig. 2). In addition, a higher proportion of saplings had reached the reproductive stage in
310 PCL than in the other treatments (20% in PCL vs. 4% in NI and SL; $P=0.0009$). Cone
311 production was also greater in PCL than in the other treatments ($P=0.0004$; Fig. 2).

312 Foliar carbon and nutrient concentrations in the leaf cohorts produced during the
 313 second and third growing seasons after seedling establishment were not significantly
 314 affected by the treatments (Appendix A).

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316 3.2. C, O and N isotope composition of pine needles

317 The C and O isotope ratios of pine needles of the 2008 cohort were significantly
 318 affected by the post-fire management treatments (Table 1, Fig. 3). Leaf $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ was highest
 319 in the SL treatment and lowest in the NI treatment, with intermediate values in PCL (Fig.
 320 3). Leaf $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ was lower in PCL than in the other two treatments (Fig. 3). Within
 321 treatments, we found a strong positive correlation between leaf $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ in SL
 322 ($r=0.51$; $P=0.002$), and a weaker but still significant correlation in NI ($r=0.32$; $P=0.065$). By
 323 contrast, leaf $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ were uncorrelated in the PCL treatment ($r=0.09$; $P=0.617$).
 324 Leaf $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ was positively correlated with foliar N concentration ($r=0.45$, $P=0.006$) and with
 325 foliar P concentrations ($r=0.44$; $P=0.008$) in PCL, but not in the other treatments.

326 Across treatments, leaf $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ was negatively associated with seedling growth
 327 variables, including leader-shoot elongation ($r=-0.36$; $P=0.0002$), total seedling height ($r=-$
 328 0.29 ; $P=0.003$) and leader-shoot biomass ($r=-0.19$; $P=0.048$). Leaf $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ was negatively
 329 associated with seedling growth variables as well, including leader-shoot biomass ($r=-$
 330 0.33 ; $P=0.001$), total seedling biomass ($r=-0.25$; $P=0.010$) and basal trunk diameter ($r=-$
 331 0.21 ; $P=0.033$). Leaf $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ was strongly positively associated with foliar N concentration
 332 ($r=0.52$; $P\leq 0.0001$), and, to a lesser extent, with foliar P concentration as well ($r=0.35$;
 333 $P=0.0002$). Leaf $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ correlated positively with growth variables such as total seedling
 334 height ($r=0.32$; $P\leq 0.001$) and leader-shoot elongation ($r=0.23$; $P\leq 0.017$). Mean leaf $\delta^{15}\text{N}$
 335 values were highest in NI (1.03 ± 0.32), intermediate in PCL (0.76 ± 0.28) and the lowest in
 336 SL (0.19 ± 0.39), although differences among treatments were not statistically significant
 337 due to high within-treatment variability (Table 1).

338

339 4. DISCUSSION

340 The results of this study highlight the key facilitative role that burnt wood can
341 play during post-fire seedling regeneration. After three growing seasons, pine seedlings
342 showed greater growth, vigor, and size in treatments where burnt wood was left on site
343 after the fire. The benefits provided by the presence of burnt wood were clearly
344 corroborated by large differences in sapling growth and reproductive capacity among
345 post-fire management treatments after six years. Furthermore, the combined
346 measurement of growth variables, leaf-nutrient concentrations, and isotopic ratios in
347 naturally regenerating seedlings offered valuable insights into the potential
348 ecophysiological mechanisms underlying the effects of different post-fire management
349 treatments on tree regeneration.

350

351 *4.1. Effect of burnt woody debris on seedling-water relations*

352 Leaf $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ data strongly suggest a key role of burnt coarse woody debris in
353 alleviating drought stress during pine seedling establishment. High foliar $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\delta^{18}\text{O}$
354 values and a tight positive correlation between $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ (indicative of strong
355 stomatal limitation of both photosynthesis and transpiration; Barbour et al., 2002; Grams
356 et al., 2007; Scheidegger et al., 2000) indicate that pine seedlings were severely water
357 stressed in the SL treatment. By contrast, seedlings in the PCL treatment were
358 considerably less water stressed, as indicated by lower foliar $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ values and a
359 lack of correlation between $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ values. Seedlings in the NI treatment showed
360 intermediate results, with only weak correlation between leaf $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\delta^{18}\text{O}$. Closer
361 proximity and contact between burnt woody debris and soil in PCL than in NI may have
362 contributed to more effective microclimate amelioration and soil-moisture retention in
363 the PCL treatment during the first years after the wildfire (Fontaine et al., 2010; Harmon
364 et al., 1986; Maser and Trappe, 1984; Smaill et al., 2008), thus explaining the differences
365 in seedling performance between these two treatments. In a previous paper, we reported
366 that the presence of burnt logs, branches, and in general post-fire coarse woody debris,
367 reduced solar radiation at ground level and soil temperature in the study area (Castro et
368 al., 2011). This in turn reduces soil-water evaporation, and consequently increases soil-

369 water availability for the establishing seedlings, which is especially relevant to warm dry
370 sites with high solar radiation as in the present study (Mediterranean climate and SW aspect).
371 The results of the present study provide insight into the ecophysiological mechanisms
372 underlying the differential seedling responses to various post-fire management practices.

373

374 *4.2. Effects of burnt woody debris on nutrient acquisition*

375 The biogeochemical role of burnt wood also may have contributed to between-
376 treatment differences in post-fire seedling performance. Burnt logs and woody debris
377 represent a potential source of nutrients that are progressively released to the soil during
378 decomposition (Ganjugunte et al., 2004; Marañón-Jiménez and Castro, 2013; Palviainen et
379 al., 2010a, 2010b). In this sense, the trend towards higher leaf $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ in the unsalvaged
380 treatment can denote an enhancement of N mineralization and, ultimately, a more active
381 N cycling among soil, plants, and soil microorganisms (Craine et al., 2009) in treatments
382 where burnt wood was left onsite. Moreover, although we found no significant
383 differences in foliar nutrient concentrations among treatments, the larger biomass of
384 seedlings in the unsalvaged treatments implies a higher total nutrient uptake. This
385 suggests that the presence of burnt wood can also enhance the growth of naturally
386 regenerating pine seedlings as a consequence of the improvement of soil fertility and
387 nutrient availability (Marañón-Jiménez et al., 2013; Marañón-Jiménez and Castro, 2013).
388 Notably, the above-mentioned absence of correlation between foliar $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ in the
389 PCL treatment was accompanied by a strong positive correlation between $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and foliar
390 N concentration (which was not observed in the rest of the treatments). Then, for
391 seedlings in the PCL treatment, higher $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values point out to increased water-use
392 efficiency as a result of enhanced carboxylative capacity and net photosynthetic rate,
393 rather than reduced stomatal conductance as in the SL treatment (Dawson et al., 2002;
394 Field and Mooney, 1986; Scheidegger et al., 2000).

395 Nutrient release from wood is, nonetheless, a relatively slow and incremental
396 process that is limited by slow decomposition rates in water-limited ecosystems (Harmon
397 et al., 1986; Marañón-Jiménez and Castro, 2013; Weedon et al., 2009). Thus, seedling
398 growth stimulation by an enhanced nutrient supply from decaying wood is not expected

399 to be substantial during the first years after the fire, but will increase in subsequent years
400 as the decaying wood releases its nutrients. Our results support this hypothesis, as
401 differences in pine growth among treatments (and particularly between PCL and SL)
402 increased over time, ranging from non-significant two years after seedling emergence
403 (leader-shoot elongation in 2007) to sharp differences after three or six years (2008 and
404 2011 data). The closer contact of wood with soil in PCL relative to NI during these first
405 years in which dead trees were still standing could have contributed to greater seedling
406 growth in PCL as a consequence of higher nutrient release and soil fertility (*e.g.*
407 Marañón-Jiménez and Castro, 2013). Therefore, the results show that tree felling and
408 rearranging post-fire woody debris over the ground surface may shift the positive role of
409 residual wood earlier in time with PCL versus NI, but further study is needed to
410 determine if this difference persists through time. In any case, the positive effects of the
411 presence of burnt coarse woody debris from a biogeochemical perspective may increase
412 over time for a number of years after fire, gaining relevance as wood slowly decomposes.
413

414 *4.3. Burnt woody debris as nurse objects to facilitate seedling establishment*

415 The results of this study support our working hypotheses, showing that burnt logs
416 and branches left on site after the fire can improve pine seedling establishment and
417 growth by both reducing water stress and increasing nutrient availability. In the context
418 of facilitation theory, these inanimate structures act as nurse objects for pine seedlings
419 (Castro et al., 2011). Facilitation is recognized as an ecological mechanism that improves
420 seedling performance for at least one of the interacting species (Brooker et al., 2008;
421 Callaway, 2007). However, the facilitative interaction must be considered the net result
422 of both positive (*e.g.* amelioration of microclimatic conditions) and negative (*e.g.* above-
423 ground or below-ground competition) forces acting between the counterparts (Callaway,
424 1998; Callaway and Walker, 1997; Cranston et al., 2012; Holmgren et al., 1997).
425 Numerous studies support the idea that facilitation in water-stressed environments is
426 driven by the amelioration of microclimatic conditions supplied by the canopy of nurse
427 plants, despite a simultaneous negative below-ground effect of the root competition for

428 water and nutrients (Armas and Pugnaire, 2009; Callaway, 1992; Franzese et al., 2009;
429 Gómez-Aparicio et al., 2005; Maestre et al., 2003; Padilla and Pugnaire, 2008; Rey-
430 Benayas, 1998). From this perspective, burnt coarse woody debris is particularly effective
431 as nurse structures, as it provides the multiple benefits of improving microclimatic
432 conditions without competition, while even increasing soil fertility through nutrient
433 release. Previous studies in the same area have reported higher survival of both planted
434 and naturally regenerating seedlings in the presence of burnt logs and branches scattered
435 on the ground (PCL treatment; Castro et al., 2011; Leverkus et al., 2012). Positive effects
436 of burnt coarse woody debris on seedling recruitment and survival have also been
437 reported in other regions (Beghin et al., 2010; Brown et al., 2003; Coop and Schoettle,
438 2009; Donato et al., 2006; Harmon et al., 1986; Marzano et al., 2013). Moreover, foresters
439 have planted tree seedlings under logs and stumps, snags, logs and rocks (*i.e.*, 'micro-
440 siting') for a long time (Wisconsin Dept. Natural Resources, 1990). In summary, burnt
441 wood left on site after a fire, whether logs, branches, or coarse woody debris that might
442 persist after post-fire human management, should be regarded as nurse objects with the
443 potential to foster plant regeneration.

444

445 *4.4. Management implications*

446 The application of facilitation theory to promote natural forest regeneration or to
447 increase ecological restoration success has advanced significantly in the last decade
448 (Castro et al., 2002, 2006; Gómez-Aparicio et al., 2004; Padilla and Pugnaire, 2006).
449 However, most of this research has focused on the use of live nurse plants that promote
450 the establishment success of a target species (Brooker et al., 2008; Gómez-Aparicio, 2009;
451 Padilla and Pugnaire, 2006), whereas little attention has been paid to inanimate natural
452 nurse structures already present in the area to be restored. Recent studies have
453 demonstrated the positive effects that inanimate objects can have for seedling survival
454 and performance by ameliorating the microclimate and reducing runoff, thereby
455 increasing plant-available water for seedlings (Harrington et al., 2013). Natural inanimate
456 objects offering potential for facilitation include rocks, boulders, terrace risers (Carlucci

457 et al., 2011; Coop and Schoettle, 2009; Munguía- Peters et al., 2008; Resler et al., 2005;
458 Rosas and Sosa, 2008; Smit et al., 2008), piles of cut branches mimicking nurse canopies
459 (Gómez-Aparicio et al., 2005; Padilla and Pugnaire, 2008), or even branches spread on the
460 ground as a result of pruning activity (Castro et al., 2011; Harrington et al., 2013; Hastings
461 et al., 2003; Jacobs and Gatewood, 1999; Stoddard et al., 2008). Moreover, the structural
462 habitats provided by dead logs and branches in disturbed forest areas (whether from fire
463 or other disturbances such as insect outbreaks, droughts, windstorms, etc.) may attract
464 animal seed dispersers, further increasing the positive effects on seedling recruitment
465 (Carlucci et al., 2011; Castro et al., 2010b, 2012; Cavallero et al., 2013; Rost et al., 2009,
466 2010), and also potentially reducing herbivore damage to the regenerating vegetation
467 (Relva et al., 2009; Ripple and Larsen, 2001). The potential of facilitation by dead tree
468 structures resulting from different disturbances for ecological restoration is very large at
469 the global scale. Fires, insect outbreaks, diseases, windstorms, drought-induced tree
470 mortality, etc. affect large areas of forest globally every year (e.g. Allen et al., 2010;
471 Bowman et al., 2009; Froking et al., 2009), often leaving a substantial aftermath of dead
472 woody structures in post-disturbance ecosystems – land managers could use this residual
473 wood to achieve restoration objectives (Brewer, 2008; Brown et al., 2003; Graham et al.,
474 1994). In this context, the positive effects of microclimatic amelioration by coarse woody
475 debris, plus the benefits provided by nutrient release from wood, have much untapped
476 potential for fostering ecosystem recovery and ecological restoration after severe fires and
477 other forest disturbances.

478

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491

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794 FIGURE CAPTIONS
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797 FIGURE 1. Growth variables of the pine seedlings. Leader shoot growth during the second
798 (2007) and third (2008) growing season after the wildfire (a-d) and total height in 2008 (three
799 growing seasons after the wildfire) (e) in the different post-fire treatments of burnt wood. NI:
800 non-intervention, PCL: partial cut plus lopping, SL: salvage logging. Different letters above
801 bars indicate significant differences among treatments (Tukey HSD test after mixed
802 ANOVAs).
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 805 FIGURE 2. Growth variables and cone production of the pine saplings. Annual growth (a),
 806 cone production (b) and total height (c) of the pines measured in 2012 (six growing seasons
 807 after the wildfire) in the different post-fire treatments of burnt wood. Annual growth was
 808 measured as the leader-shoot elongation during the previous growing season of 2011. NI:
 809 non-intervention, PCL: partial cut plus lopping, SL: salvage logging. Different letters above
 810 bars indicate significant differences among treatments (Tukey HSD test after mixed
 811 ANOVAs and Kruskal-Wallis test).
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 814 FIGURE 3. Leaf isotopic composition of pine seedlings. Carbon (a) and oxygen (b) isotopic
 815 composition of pine seedling needles from the part of leader-shoot elongated in 2008 in the
 816 different post-fire treatments of burnt wood. NI: non-intervention, PCL: partial cut plus
 817 lopping, SL: salvage logging. Different letters above bars indicate significant differences
 818 among treatments, $P=0.003$ and $P=0.064$ for carbon and oxygen respectively (Tukey HSD
 819 test after mixed ANOVAs).